

An Investigation into the Challenges Militating Against Implementation of Secondary School Educational Policies in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja, Nigeria

AUTHOR(S): OGUNODE NIYI JACOB, DEBORAH JEGEDE

Abstract

The study investigated the challenges facing militating against implementation of educational policies of secondary school education in F.C.T, Abuja. The study adopted descriptive survey research design. The population of the study comprised 18 secondary schools in FCT. The sample for the study was 180 teachers selected from 18 secondary schools. The sample was drawn through randomly and proportionate random sampling techniques. A self-developed instrument of seven items question titled "Challenges Facing Educational Policies Implementation in FCT. Questionnaire" (CFEPIFCTQ) which was answered by teachers was used for the study. The reliability of the instrument was established through test-retest method. This was done by administering the instrument twice within an interval of two weeks to 30 teachers in Kogi state. The two sets of responses were correlated using Pearson's Product Moment Correlation and a reliability coefficient of 0.75 was obtained. The data collected was analyzed through the simple percentage. The result collected, analyzed and collected from the table led to the conclusion that inadequate funding, inadequate professional teachers, inadequate infrastructural facilities, institutional corruption, political instability, poor planning, poor supervision and inspection and lack of political will are the challenges militating against implementation of educational policies of secondary school education in F.C.T, Abuja.

Keywords: Challenges, Educational policies, secondary schools, Education,

CJAR

Accepted 26 February 2021
Published 28 February 2021
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4648439

About Author

Author(s): OGUNODE NIYI JACOB

Federal University Wukari, Nigeria.

E-MAIL: Ogunodejacob@gmail.com

DEBORAH JEGEDE

Post-graduate Student, University of Abuja, Nigeria.

E-MAIL: Jegededeborah30@gmail.com

1.0 Introduction

Secondary Education is a kind of the education that children receive after primary education and before the tertiary education. Based on the 6-3-3-4 system of education, secondary education it comprises six years duration, but given in two stages: a junior secondary school stage and a senior secondary school stage, each to run for three years duration.

The broad goals of Secondary Education according to the National Policy on Education (2014) include, the preparation of the individual for:

- i. Useful living within the society and
- ii. Higher education.

In specific terms, the objectives are to: to provide all primary school leavers with the opportunity for education of a higher level, irrespective of sex, social status, religion or ethnic background; to offer diversified curriculum to cater for the differences in talents, opportunities and future roles; to provide trained manpower in the applied science, technology and commerce at sub-professional grades; to develop and promote Nigerian languages, art and culture in the context of world cultural heritage; to inspire its students with a desire for self-improvement and achievement of excellence; to foster national unity with an emphasis on the common ties that unite us in our diversity; to raise a generation of people who can think for themselves, respect the view and feelings of others, respect the dignity of labour, appreciate those values specified under our broad national goals and live as good citizens; and to provide technical knowledge and vocational skills necessary for agricultural, industrial, commercial and economic development (Noun, 2009).

The Secondary school education policies in Nigeria is contained in the National policy on Education section three. This section contains policies on administration and management of secondary schools in Nigeria. It is observed that there are challenges facing the implementation of the secondary school education in Nigeria and in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja, Nigeria. This study is aimed to investigate the challenges militating against implementation of secondary schools education policies in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja, Nigeria.

1.1. Research Objectives

The aim of this study is to investigate the challenges militating against implementation of educational policies of secondary school education in F.C.T, Abuja, Nigeria. Specific objectives are to:

1. To find out if the inadequate funding is a challenge militating against implementation of educational policies of secondary school education in F.C.T, Abuja;
2. To find out if inadequate professional teachers is a challenge militating against implementation of educational policies of secondary school education in F.C.T, Abuja;
3. To find out if inadequate infrastructural facilities is a challenge militating against implementation of educational policies of secondary school education in F.C.T, Abuja
4. To find out if institutional corruption is a challenge militating against implementation of educational policies of secondary school education in F.C.T, Abuja
5. To find out if political instability is a challenge militating against implementation of educational policies of secondary school education in F.C.T, Abuja
6. To find out if poor planning is a challenge militating against implementation of educational policies of secondary school education in F.C.T, Abuja and
7. To find out if poor supervision and inspection is a challenge militating against implementation of educational policies of secondary school education in F.C.T, Abuja

8. To find out if lack of political will is a challenge militating against implementation of educational policies of secondary school education in F.C.T, Abuja

1.2 Research Question

The study were guided with the following questions:

1. Is inadequate funding is a challenge militating against implementation of educational policies of secondary school education in F.C.T, Abuja?;
2. Is inadequate professional teachers is a challenge militating against implementation of educational policies of secondary school education in F.C.T, Abuja?;
3. Is inadequate infrastructural facilities is a challenge militating against implementation of educational policies of secondary school education in F.C.T, Abuja?
4. Is institutional corruption is a challenge militating against implementation of educational policies of secondary school education in F.C.T, Abuja?
5. Is political instability is a challenge militating against implementation of educational policies of secondary school education in F.C.T, Abuja?
6. Is poor planning is a challenge militating against implementation of educational policies of secondary school education in F.C.T, Abuja; ?
7. Is poor supervision and inspection is a challenge militating against implementation of educational policies of secondary school education in F.C.T, Abuja? ; and
8. Is lack of political will is a challenge militating against implementation of educational policies of secondary school education in F.C.T, Abuja?

1.3 Statement of Research Programme

Secondary school education is the post-primary school education. Secondary school education is the education that prepare the students for the higher institutions. Secondary school education is key to the social, economic and technological advancement of the country. To achieve the objective of the secondary school in Nigeria, the federal government formulated policies to guide the administration and management of secondary school. The major aims of the secondary school education policies to ensure quality education in the secondary schools. There are many challenges facing the implementation of this secondary school policies across the country and in FCT in particularly. This study is design to investigate challenges militating against implementation of educational policies of secondary school education in F.C.T, Abuja, Nigeria.

2.0 Literature Review

2.1 Concept of Educational Policies

Educational policies are policies designed to aid smooth implementation of education programme. Educational policies are policies formulated to give direction to the administration of educational programme. Educational policies are backed by laws fir the regulation and educational programme. Educational policies are used to realize the objectives of education. Noun (2011) defined educational policy of Nigeria as a general statement containing principles, regulations and rules, that govern many of the decisions on education on how to educate children, where to get them educated, where to get them employed, who to teach them, how to finance their education, what to teach, how to impart skills, goals, objectives and even the philosophy. Educational policies are initiatives mostly by governments that determine the direction of an educational system (Okoroma 2000)

2.1 Concept of Implementation

Implementation is the systematic ways of carrying out planned document or programme. Implementation is the act of executing policies, programme and programme. Implementation is the process of coordinating activities of carrying out drafted planned, policies and

pogramme. In educational institutions, implementation is a must. Planned educational policies and programme must be implemented to realize the objectives of education. Implementation in education must follow a defined processes and pattern to be succesful.

There are many investigations on educational policies implementation and challenges in Nigeria. Okoroma (2003) outline the constraints that impeded effective implementation of UBE programme to include: inadequate qualified teachers, inadequate funds, inadequate teaching and learning facilities, lack of professional guidance and counselling teachers and poor motivation of teachers.

These observable constraints affecting implementation of educational policies in Nigeria, according to the Ogunode & Adah (2020) identified the following as the challenges affecting the implementation of educational policies in Nigeria to include : institutional corruption, inadequate funding, shortage of professional teachers, lack of political will, political instability, poor policy formulation, insecurity, lack of continuity in commitment to policy implementation and poor relationship between policy designer and policy implementer.

According to Manafa, (2011) lack of amenities (electricity), inadequate personnel, incessant political changes, mismanagement of funds, lack of continuity of policy, lack of physical plant, problem of record keeping, quota system makes qualified students not to get admission, inadequate funds, government making over-ambitious policy goals, poor monitoring and supervision of schools, bribery and corruption in the system and incessant political changes. Other problem include over population of students in Federal Government College, pressure on politicians to satisfy their constituencies in return for continued political support, educationally advantaged and disadvantaged states denies students admission into schools, complete neglect of teaching profession, lack of commitment to duty among teachers, inadequate provision of instructional materials, mismanagement of funds, inadequate provision of science laboratories equipment and facilities and poor motivation of teachers.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

The study adopted descriptive survey research design. The population of the study comprised 18 secondary schools in FCT. The sample for the study was 180 teachers selected from 18 secondary schools. The sample was drawn through randomly and propoortionate random sampling techniques.

In all the six area councils in FCT, 18 public secondary schools were randomly selected from the six area councils in FCT. This was followed by proportionate selection of three secondary schools per Local Government Area, making 18 schools, 180 teachers were thereafter selected using simple random sampling technique at the rate of 10 teachers per school. A self-developed instrument of 30 items titled "Challenges Facing Educational Policies Implementation in FCT. Questionnaire" (CFEPIFCTQ) which was answered by teachers was used for the study. Both face and content validity were established by experts from University of Abuja. A two point adapted Likert-scale of measurement was used thus: Strongly agree (SA) and strongly disagree (SD). The reliability of the instrument was established through test-retest method. This was done by administering the instrument twice within an internal of two weeks to 30 teachers in Kogi state. The two sets of responses were correlated using Pearson's Product Moment Correlation and a reliability coefficient of 0.75 was obtained. The data collected was analyzed through the simple percentage.

4.0 RESULTS

4.1 RESULT ANALYSIS

Research Question: The following are the challenges militating against implementation of secondary school education policies in FCT

S/N	ITEMS	Strongly Agree (%)	Strongly Disagree (%)
1.	Inadequate funding is a challenge militating against implementation of educational policies of secondary school education in F.C.T, Abuja	180 (100)	-
2.	Inadequate professional teachers is a challenge militating against implementation of educational policies Of secondary school education in F.C.T, Abuja	162 (90)	18 (10)
3.	Inadequate infrastructural facilities is a challenge militating against implementation of educational policies of secondary school education in F.C.T, Abuja	180 (100)	-
4.	Institutional corruption is a challenge militating against implementation of educational policies of secondary school education in F.C.T, Abuja	143 (79)	37 (21)
5.	Political instability is a challenge militating against implementation of educational policies of secondary school education in F.C.T, Abuja	168 (93)	12 (7.0)
6.	Poor planning is a challenge militating against implementation of educational policies of secondary school education in F.C.T, Abuja	135 (75)	45 (25)
7.	Poor supervision and inspection a challenge militating against implementation of educational policies of secondary school education in F.C.T, Abuja.	180 (67)	-
8.	Lack of political will is a challenge militating against implementation of educational policies of secondary school education in F.C.T, Abuja.	121 (67)	59 (33)

4.2 Result Analysis

Result collected from table 180 (100) item one revealed that all the sampled respondents agreed that inadequate funding is one of the major challenges militating against implementation of educational policies of secondary school education in FCT. This implies that 100% of the respondents agreed that inadequate funding is a challenge militating against implementation of educational policies of secondary school education in FCT.

Table 1 item two result showed that 162 (90%) of the respondents agreed that inadequate professional teachers is one of the major challenges militating against implementation of educational policies of secondary school education in FCT while 18 (10%) of the respondents disagreed. This implies that majorities of the respondents agreed that inadequate professional teachers is a challenge militating against implementation of educational policies of secondary school education in FCT.

Result collected from table 1 item three with 180 (100) indicated that all the sampled respondents agreed that inadequate infrastructural facilities is one of the major challenges militating against implementation of educational policies of secondary school education in FCT. This implies that 100% of the respondents agreed that inadequate infrastructural facilities is a challenge militating against implementation of educational policies of secondary school education in FCT.

Information from table 1 item four disclosed that 143 (79%) of the respondents were of the opinion that institutional corruption is constitutes a challenge that is militating against implementation of educational policies of secondary school education in FCT while 37 (21%) of the respondents had a contrary opinion. This implies that majorities of the respondents agreed that institutional corruption is a challenge militating against implementation of educational policies of secondary school education in FCT.

The result obtained from table 1 item five disclosed that 168 (93%) of the sampled teachers ticked agreed that political instability is militating against implementation of educational policies of secondary school education in FCT and 12 (7.0%) did not agree that political instability is militating against implementation of educational policies of secondary school education in FCT, The result collected here showed that majorities of the respondents agreed that political instability is militating against implementation of educational policies of secondary school education in FCT.

From item six table 1 revealed that majorities of the respondents were of the view that poor planning is among the challenges facing implementation of educational policies of secondary school education in FCT 135 (75%) while 45 (25) of the respondents were of the opposite view that poor planning is among the challenges facing implementation of educational policies of secondary school education in FCT. This means that majorities of the respondents agreed that poor planning is militating effective implementation of educational policies of secondary school education in FCT.

Table 1 item seven on poor supervision and inspection as a challenge militating against implementation of secondary school educational policies in FCT disclosed that 180 (100%) of the respondents agreed that poor supervision and inspection is among the major challenges militating against implementation of educational policies of secondary school education in FCT.

Table 1 item eight result indicated that 121 (67%) of the respondents agreed that lack of political will is one of the major challenges militating against implementation of educational policies of secondary school education in FCT while 59 (33%) of the respondents disagreed that that lack of political will is one of the major challenges militating against implementation of educational policies of secondary school education in FCT. This implies that majorities of the respondents agreed that lack of political will is a challenge militating against implementation of educational policies of secondary school education in FCT.

4.3 Discussion of Result

To find out if inadequate funding is one of the major challenges militating against implementation of educational policies of secondary school education in FCT. Resulted collected showed that 100% of the respondents agreed that inadequate funding is a challenge militating against implementation of educational policies of secondary school education in FCT. This is in line with Ogba and Igu (2014), Keller (2012) and Ogunode (2021) who submitted that inadequate funding is a major problem facing the administration of secondary school in Nigeria. The budgetary allocation for the administration and implementation of secondary policies and programme is not enough.

To find out if inadequate professional teachers is one of the major challenges militating against implementation of educational policies of secondary school education in FCT. Information obtained disclosed that all the respondents accepted that inadequate professional teachers is a challenge militating against implementation of educational policies of secondary school education in FCT. This result is in agreement with Odia and Omofonmwan (2007), Ige (2012), and Ogunode, (2021) who concluded that inadequate professional teachers is another challenge preventing the implementation of the secondary school education in Nigeria. The scarcity of science teachers is a major problem facing the implementation of science policies and programme in the secondary school education in Nigeria.

Result collected on if inadequate infrastructural facilities is among the major challenges militating against implementation of educational policies of secondary school education in FCT showed that 100% of the respondents agreed that inadequate infrastructural facilities is a challenge militating against implementation of educational policies of secondary school education in FCT. This finding support the submission of Ogunode & Adah (2020) and Ige (2011) who observed that another challenge facing the secondary school administration is inadequate infrastructural facilities. It is impossible for the secondary school to implement their programme and policies without adequate infrastructural facilities available.

Table 1 item four on to find out if institutional corruption is constituting a challenge against implementation of educational policies of secondary school education in FCT. Result collected showed that majorities of the respondents agreed that institutional corruption is a challenge militating against implementation of educational policies of secondary school education in FCT. Ogunode & Adah (2020) and Ogunode (2021) submitted that there many problems facing secondary school administration in Nigeria and these problems include; institutions corruption, inadequate teachers, shortage of instructional resources, insecurity, inadequate data for planning and inadequate funding.

To find out if political instability is militating against implementation of educational policies of secondary school education in FCT. The result collected here revealed that majorities of the respondents agreed that political instability is militating against implementation of educational policies of secondary school education in FCT. Ogunode & Adah (2020) and

Ogunode (2021) who observed that political instability is a very serious problem facing the educational sector in Nigeria. Many educational policies and programme have been abandon because of political instability. The changes in political administration or government affects the educational policies of the country because the new government is coming with new policies and new programme.

To find out if poor planning is among the challenges facing implementation of educational policies of secondary school education in FCT. Result obtained from table 1 item six indicated that the majorities of the respondents agreed that poor planning is militating effective implementation of educational policies of secondary school education in FCT. This discovery support the submission of Okoroma (2006) who opined that the gap that often exists between policy formulation and implementation provokes inquiry to identify factors that constrain the effective implementation of educational policies. The problem of policy implementation is traceable to the planning stage which comes immediately after policy formulation

To find out if poor supervision and inspection is a challenge militating against implementation of secondary school educational policies in FCT. The result collected revealed that all the respondents agreed that poor supervision and inspection is among the major challenges militating against implementation of educational policies of secondary school education in FCT. Ogunode, Adah, Pajo & Audu (2020) did an article that looked at challenges preventing effective monitoring and evaluation of education in Nigeria and they identified the challenges to include; inadequate funding of monitoring and evaluation programme, inadequate professional monitoring and evaluating officers, poor capacity development of monitoring and evaluating officers, corruptions, insecurity, inadequate monitoring and evaluation tools, political instability and lack of political support.

To find out if lack of political will is one of the major challenges militating against implementation of educational policies of secondary school education in FCT. Information collected from this table disclosed that the majorities of the respondents agreed that lack of political will is a challenge militating against implementation of educational policies of secondary school education in FCT. Lack of political will is responsible for the poor implementation of many education programme and policies in Nigeria. Nigerian politician lack the political will to implement some educational policies and this is affecting the development of education in the country (UNICEF, 2017, Ogunode & Adah (2020).

5.0 Conclusion

Secondary school according to National policy on education (2004) is the post-primary school education. Secondary school education is designed to prepare the students for higher education. Secondary school education is vital to the social, economic and technological development of the country.

The Secondary school education policies in Nigeria is contained in the National policy on Education section three. This section contains policies on administration and management of secondary schools in Nigeria. It is observed that there are challenges facing the implementation of the secondary school education in Nigeria and in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja, Nigeria. This study was designed to investigate the challenges militating against implementation of secondary school educational policies in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja, Nigeria.

The result collected, analyzed and collected from the table led to the conclusion that inadequate funding, inadequate professional teachers, inadequate infrastructural facilities, institutional corruption, political instability, poor planning, poor supervision and inspection and lack of political will are the challenges militating against implementation of secondary school educational policies in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja, Nigeria.

5.1 Recommendation

Based on this findings, the papers recommends the following:

- a) The government should increase the funding of secondary school education in Federal capital Territory, Abuja and in Nigeria as a whole. This will help to provide all educational resources needed for the implementation of secondary school education policies in Federal capital Territory, Abuja and in Nigeria as a whole;
- b) The government should employ more professional teachers and deploy to all secondary schools in Federal capital Territory, Abuja and in Nigeria as a whole;
- c) The government should fight all forms of corruption in the educational institutions. This can be done through the use of the various anti-corruption agencies in the country;
- d) The government should ensure effective supervision and inspection of all secondary schools in Federal Capital Territory to ensure that secondary school policies are fully implemented;
- e) The government should ensure a political environment that will guarantee policies stability and political stability.

References

- Adesina, S. (1977). *Planning and educational development in Nigeria*, Ibadan: Education Industries (Nigeria) Ltd.
- Aghenta, J.A. (1984). Towards a systems approach to the planning of secondary education in Nigeria', in Adesina, Segun and Ogusaju (eds.), *Secondary education in Nigeria*, Ile Ife: University of Ife Press.
- Federal Ministry of Education (2004): National policy of education, Lagos: NERDC
- Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN, 2008): *The National Policy on Education*. Lagos, National Educational Research and Development centre (NERDC).
- Ige, A. M. (2011). Myths and realities of falling standard of education in Nigeria: The way forward. *Nigerian Journal of Professional Teachers*, 2, 36-48.
- Keller, B. Y. (2012). Factors associated with high school learners' poor performance: A spotlight on mathematics and social studies. *South African Journal of Education*, 27(4), 233-242.
- Manafa, I, F. (2011).The administrative constraints to policy implementation in federal government colleges in south east Nigeria. Thesis, University of Nigeria, Nsukka.
- Noun (2012). *Evaluation Strategies in Educational Planning and Implementation*. Lagos, Nigeria
- Noun (2010). *Implementation of educational policy plans*. Lagos, Nigeria

- NOUN (2009). *Concepts and Theories of Educational Administration and Planning*. Lagos, Nigeria.
- NEEDS, (2014). *Needs assessment in the Nigerian education sector*. International organization for migration, Abuja, Nigeria.
- Obi, E. (2003). *Educational management: Theory and practice*. Enugu: Jamoe Enterprise.
- Odia, L. O., & Omofonmwan, S. I. (2007). Educational system in Nigeria: Problems and prospects. *Journal of Social Sciences*, 14(1), 81-86.
- Osokoya, O.I. (1987). *6-3-3-4 education in Nigeria: history, strategies, issues and problems*, Lagos: Bininaike Educational Publishers.
- Ololube, N. P. (2013). The Problems and Approaches to Educational Planning in Nigeria: A Theoretical Observation. *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences MCSER Publishing, Rome-Italy* Vol 4, 12, 89
- Okoroma, N.S. (2001). 'An evaluation study of the 3-3 aspect of the National Policy on Education in Port Harcourt and Obio/Akpor Local Government areas of Rivers State', *Journal of Technical and Science Education*, vol. 10, nos. 1 & 2.
- Okoroma N. S. (2006) Educational policies and problems of implementation in Nigeria. *Australian Journal of Adult Learning* Volume 46, Number 2.
- Okoroma, N.S. (2003). 'Factors militating against the effective implementation of the basic education programme in Rivers State', unpublished paper.
- Ogunode, N., Gregory D., & Abubakar, M. (2020). Assessment of political officeholders' attitudes towards planning of education in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja. Nigeria. *Journal of Educational Research in Developing Areas*, 1 (1), 68-79.
- Ogunode, N.J. (2020). *Challenges facing the planning of early childhood care education in nigeria and the ways forward*. Lamb Publisher.
- Ogunode, N.J, Adah, S, Pajo, W & Audu, I (2020) Monitoring and Evaluation of Education in Nigeria: Challenges and Ways Forwards. *Journal On Orange Technologies*, Volume: 02 Issue: 02, P:8-16
- Ukeje, B.O. (1985). 'The 6-3-3-4 education system: the objectives and prospects', paper presented at the National Conference on the 6-3-3-4 Education System at A.I.C.E. Owerri.
- Ukeje, B.O. (1986). *School and society in Nigeria*, Enugu: Fourth Dimension Publishing Co. Ltd.
- Van Horn, C.E. & Van Meter, D.S. (1977). 'The implementation of intergovernmental policy', *Policy Studies Review*, vol. 1, London: Stage Publications.

UNESCO (2012). World Bank selected 20 countries' annual budgetary allocation to education. Washington D.C.: The World Bank

Cite this article:

Author(s), OGUNODE NIYI JACOB, DEBORAH JEGEDE, (2021). "An Investigation into the Challenges Militating Against Implementation of Secondary School Educational Policies in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja, Nigeria". **Name of the Journal:** Commonwealth Journal of Academic Research, (CJAR.EU), P, 1- 12. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4648439> , Issue: 2, Vol.: 2, Article: 1, Month: February, Year: 2021. Retrieved from <https://www.cjar.eu/all-issues/>

Published by

AND

ThoughtWares Consulting & Multi Services International (TWCMSI)

